

Seeking Authentic Bengali Taste of Horror: A Survey Through the Corners of *Jekhane Bhooter Bhoy*

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Abstract

The history of Bengal boasts of an affluent blend of culture and ethnic identity. The culture is richly endowed with a divergent array of equipment even for contemplation purpose as well, as vivid as the affair concerning Bengali ghosts. In Bengal, ghosts are termed as Bhoot, and for the other supernatural entities, the term is Pret. From Pret-Aatma to Kankal, it can be traced how the ethnicity of the culture has determined the classification of ghosts vehemently. Tales of frightening ghosts exist in Bengal, but the episodes of comic supernatural entities are present at significant intervals. The entire construction is proportionally balanced. The writers of Bengal have significantly delved deep into exploring the multitude of Bhoot and Pret in their apparent settings. From children's stories of *Bhoot* and Pret to spine-chilling tales of horror, every facet of it has been taken care of. Many adaptations of these stories have been done onscreen. Sandip Ray carries the legacy of the renowned name Satyajit Ray. From inspecting his father's work to investigating other writers, Sandip Ray's storytelling onscreen has been a distinct one. One of his noted works includes *Jekhane Bhooter Bhoy* (2012). This film is an attempt at digging deep into Bengali horror, and is an anthology which consists of three different stories: two of which is written by Satyajit Ray and the last is by Sharadindu Bandyopadhyay. This paper will look into, and examine the distinctive notion of *bhoot(s)* in these three different stories, and its composite impact, as portrayed by Sandip Ray.

Keywords: Bengali, Horror, Ghosts, Bhoot, Stories.

Introduction

The corners of Bengal are enriched with cultural trademarks at large. What is the most significant aspect of it is that horror occupies a magnanimous portion of it. From oral legends to texts and films, ghosts have inhabited the roundtable discussion. Proceeding towards the different kinds of ghosts that have lived in the edges of Bengal, the belief of their origin and

the hurdle they pose on living beings have made the entire exchange intense and detailed. Even in traditional Bengali addas, the topic of ghosts hasn't lost its essence throughout the years. The adoption of storytelling is purposefully done to generate the interest of the people around, and the tenure has even given rise to a popular radio show initiated by Radio Mirchi named *The Sunday Suspense*. This is a show where horror literary texts are mostly adapted and the RJs enact the characters and develop an entire episode. The mobilization of this show has consistently flared the enthusiasm of its audience. Even the long duration of the episodes couldn't deter its appeal, and some of the most sought-after stories of Sunday Suspense enjoy a substantial length altogether. What is compelling in this narrative is that the core of horror lies in the engagement of the readers, listeners and viewers. Satyajit Ray, the renowned face of Bengali films has written various anthologies of tales, and horror is allotted a significant segment from it. A decent attempt by Sandip Ray in terms of horror is *Jekhane Bhooter Bhoy* (2012). It is an amalgamation of three different horror tales which is woven into a film: the first two are adapted through Ray's stories and the third is a tale by Sharadindu Bondhopadhyay.

The key objectives of this research paper are:

1. To examine the varied representation of horror in these films.
2. To understand its nuances in the storyline.
3. To analyse the composite impact of the film that delves into Bengali horror.

Literature review

The years (2012-2013) has been notable in terms of Bengali films finally having access to some of the most impressive films that explores the core of Bengali horror.

Bhooter Bhabisyat (2013) is a horror-comedy by Anik Dutta, which scrutinizes the problems of ghosts of Bengal who are trying to survive amongst the demolition of haunted houses, and the rapid growth of high-rise buildings. For one such haunted mansion, an interview is conducted by the inhabitants for its final residents. The ghosts are selected as per their origin, identities, and the convincing roles they will play in the daily operation of the household. The events commence, and a problem arises when a greedy promoter lays his eyes on the mansion. All the ghosts gather to fight against him. The story is narrated to a film-maker and the climax features his suspicion when he receives the resources to make a film on this event. The narrator is revealed as another ghost who had concealed his identity to make the listener aware of the intricacies of the injustices faced by the class of ghosts as well.

Goynar Baksho (2013) is a horror comedy directed by Aparna Sen. An adaptation of a novel of Shirshendu Mukhhopadhyay, this film delves into the obsession with a box of gold ornaments by its owner Rashmoni. Being widowed at a young age and back to her father's zamindari household, Rashmoni's existence has conditioned around the Goynar Baksho. She refuses to let go of the box even after her death. The ghost of Rashmoni entrusts the responsibility of the box to her nephew's wife Somlata, and threatens her continuously for not

meddling with it. The five-hundred bhori worth of gold ornaments is finally handed over to Somlata's daughter Chaitali who utilizes its contents for the Mukti Bahini of Bangladeshi Liberation War.

Methodology

The methodology used in this paper to analyse the theme of horror is Narrative Analysis. This methodology seeks for an overall examination of the entire film to bring out the story it wants to let its viewers know. It studies the events of the film for its narrative structure, character and plot portrayed for the audience.

Theoretical framework

According to Alfred Hitchcock, suspense is 'the most powerful means of holding onto the viewer's attention.' As per the Standard Account Theory which has been developed by Ortony, Clore, and Collins (1998), the core of suspense is built up with three elements, i.e. fear, hope, and the cognitive state of uncertainty. To quote Aaron Smuts (2008), fear is 'the fear of displeasure about the prospect of an undesirable event' and hope is 'the feeling of pleasure about the prospect of a desirable event.' The cognitive state of uncertainty is felt when people 'fear a bad outcome, hope for a good outcome and are uncertain about which outcome will come to pass.'

Entering into the world of *Jekhane Bhooter Bhoy*

In Bengali, the title *Jekhane Bhooter Bhoy* is synonymous to Where there is a fear for ghosts. Tarinikhhuro is a significant narrator in Ray's short stories, and he is the chronicler of this film. Tarini's wanderlust has taken him on various escapades throughout his life. Thereby, his experiences have given way to his identity as a Golpo Dadu (an endearing name for a storyteller). Hardly will it be possible to limit his innumerable adventures to two books of Arabian Nights. His fan club consists of a few children who look forward to his tales. The film begins with Tarinikhhuro visiting the house of his friend to recount the tales to his fan club. He familiarizes them with the note that the day is for Bhooter Goppo (ghost stories). Tarinikhhuro classifies ghosts into four kinds, namely Oshoriri Aatma (supernatural entity which which cannot be seen), Chhaya Murti (shadow of a ghost), Niret Bhoot (looks like a human, but vanishes entirely) and Noro Kankal (skeleton which walks and talks). He has had first-hand experiences from each of this kind, but the tales he will be narrating to them aren't a result of his own experiences, but is verified altogether. Tarinikhhuro begins his first tale, informing his audience that the episode has been reported to him by his friend's son Sitesh, who had also been a witness to the entire event.

Anathbabu and his enthusiasm for probing into the nooks of *Haldarbari*

The story begins in the setting of a bus which is travelling to a village named Gobindopur. Sitesh, an upcoming writer meets Anath babu and he asks him to join in to get a glimpse of Haldar Bari, assuring jokingly that ghosts don't haunt in daylight. Sitesh gets

enlightened with the infamous history of Haldar Bari which records numerous murders, suicides, accidents etc. The entire mansion has been left vacant over ages, and an incident has sealed the place. Holodhor Dutta's son, a young man from the village had challenged his friends that he will spend a night alone at the mansion. The next morning, his body was found lifeless. Anath Babu initiates the conversation by introducing himself as a renowned ghosthunter. He has spent innumerable nights at various haunted places, and has published articles on the supernatural in celebrated journals worldwide. At the mansion, Sitesh comes across the dilapidated clock outside. The village secretary explains that Holodhor's son's lifeless body had a terrified face looking towards the Kori-Kat (ceiling). Anath Babu concludes that someone from Haldar lineage might have committed suicide there. The next day, Anath babu makes all the necessary arrangements to spend a night at the mansion. Sitesh visits the courtyard of the mansion with tea the next morning and sees Anath Babu coming out cheerfully satisfied with a neem band in his hand. He exclaims that his expedition was highly successful, and he will not have to look for ghosts anymore. He recounts the happenings of the previous night. Anath Babu didn't have a habit of sleeping at haunted houses, but he had slept here. His sleep got disturbed with the (dilapidated) clock ticking, and the damaged chair he was sleeping in, got comfortable all of a sudden. There was a hookah for him to smoke, and someone in the corner was pulling the red cloth fan over him. The entire experience was aristocratic in a manner as he claims, while Sitesh counters that this might be a dream. Anath Babu insists Sitesh to visit the room where he had spent the night. Sitesh enters the room first, and the scene features a dead Anath Babu frighteningly glancing at the Kori-Kat.

Anath babu has spent an entire lifetime searching for ghosts. He was miserable when he had been unsuccessful in his expeditions all over India. Haldar Bari was a ray of hope for him. He was distracted even his walk towards Haldar Bari, unsure of whether the place will finally deliver his urge for ghosts. But once, inside the mansion, Anath Babu asks his mates if they can weirdness in a smell, Macher Tel porar gondho (burnt smell of the skin of the fish). He ensures that ghosts are here, but they may not appear before him. Anath babu's desire for ghosts at Haldar Bari was fulfilled. But not even his entire existence had imagined him dying fearful, and eyes literally protruding out of shock, the same way Holodhor Dutta's son had. His years of experience in this field didn't provide any assistance when the final moment arrived. The viewers aren't given any clarifications regarding what Anath Babu had spotted that initiated his death, but this was so horrible that even years of experience couldn't endure the exposure. The suspense has remained intact in this manner, However, Anath Babu had died finally succumbing to the fact that he has achieved what he was looking for. He evolves into a cheerfully contented ghost who can be seen coming out of Haldar Bari in the early hours of the morning even today, so as Tarinikhuro claims. In this tale, the horror element lies in the combination of the known and unknown. The unknown is the unfamiliar occurrence in Haldar Bari, the known is Anath Babu's transformation.

Tarinikhuro's next is Brown Saheb-er Bari. This tale was narrated to him by the owner of a tea garden, Hrishikesh Mukherjee. The story commences with the reunion of two friends, Ranjan and Aniket.

Unconventional jitters in the corners of Brown Saheb's cottage

This tale begins with Ranjan visiting his friend Aniket's place in Kalimpong. When enquired about his sudden decision to visit, Ranjan informs Aniket that it is because of a diary that he has acquired from an antique shop. The diary belonged to a foreigner named Mr. Brown who lived in Evergreen lodge, and pursued his profession as a teacher in Kalimpong. His constant companion was Simon, and there has been a mention of Simon numerous times throughout the diary. A lightning strikes Simon on 22nd September, 1886 at 7:30 pm, and his body was found the next morning under a eucalyptus tree at Evergreen Lodge. Simon's sudden demise took Mr. Brown into a constant state of depression. His health worsened, and the entries in the diary became lesser in number. However, the colour of his writings undergoes a shift from blue to red on 2nd of November. 'Sitting by the fire in his favourite high-backed chair...' Simon has returned, as quoted by Mr Brown. His last entries in the diary feature him being grateful for Simon's true love for him, for it bears a testimony that Simon hasn't forgotten his companion even after death. Hrishikesh Mukherjee joins the duo, and introduces himself as a close acquaintance of Aniket. He informs that Evergreen lodge still exists in the town because its furniture was auctioned once, and sold off to one of his friends. The place may have remained vacant over years, but there are no rumours of it being a haunted house at any end. The three arrive at the lodge with significant precautions, including a gun held by Hrishikesh Mukherjee. The trio get fearful of any interruption that occurs within their premise. They become doubtful and Ranjan proposes of getting Simon's favourite chair from the furniture that has been auctioned. Hrishikesh notifies that no such chair was put up in the event. A black cat enters, sits on the chair that has emerged out of nowhere, and voices crying, 'Simon, Simon' is heard all over the room. Petrified, they leave forgetting all their belongings, even the gun behind.

It is accounted that the ghosts are to be feared, belong to humans. Simon's bravery and love are lauded numerous times in the diary, and it is made evident that Simon was Mr. Brown's only confidante. However, Simon's identity remains concealed in the diary. The trio held the belief that if Simon exists, it would be Mr. Brown's friend, son, nephew or anyone he has been close to. Nowhere in their deepest beliefs did they think Simon to be a non-human, let alone a black cat. Black cats are considered to be bad omens. They don't belong from a sphere where it is believed that they have their identities, and has the ability to haunt others apart from the omens and souls of others. The cat was inside the premises from the early hours of evening itself, but no one imagined it to be Simon. The black cat enters into the room when it is pitch dark outside. When the trio see just a cat, they laugh it off. But when the cat begins to roam, the fireplace starts to burn and a high-backed chair comes into view. This is the point when they get scared. For the initial few seconds, even the viewers become doubtful if Simon is actually the black cat or if the black cat will transform into something else. The element of suspense in this story lies in this aspect of disbelief. The voice is of Mr. Brown's, looking forward to Simon's appearance even to this day. Both of them are unable to let go of their admiration for each other's company. That enables that bond to persist consistently, beyond the barriers of life and death. The justification behind Evergreen Lodge not bearing the name of a haunted house is because a human doesn't haunt it, or maybe, nobody had imagined a

ghost to be a non-human. The horror element in this story is significantly accentuated by the tone of discovery of the unknown.

Tarikhuro resumes the third and last story in the segment by notifying his listeners that this is a substantial incident in the friend's family history as this had happened to the brother Pratap Sarkar. He had narrated his experience for the ghost had resembled Tarinikhuro himself.

The crisis of a *bhoot* and his ultimate contentment

Taking some advance from a publisher house, Pratap Sarkar goes to Raipur in search of some peaceful atmosphere to write his book. He takes a house on rent from Nikunja Paul, a rich landlord. One particular night, a ghost calls him gently. Pratap becomes scared and strikes a matchstick to make him go away. On another such appearance, the ghost comes back, introduces himself as Nanda Dulal Nandy. When asked about his intentions, Nanda Dulal Nandy informs him that his grandson lives penniless, suffers from an ailment without any chances of recovery. Nanda Dulal comes up with a proposal that the house of Nikunja Pal where he had lived earlier, has a box full of hundred Mohor (gold coins) that he had hidden while he was alive. He requests Pratap to dig the place, and bring the box to his ailing grandson. The expedition at Nikunja Lal's happens to be fruitful, and Pratap visits the place of Nanda babu's grandson. He comes across his daughter, and ensures that she is the same lady he had fallen in love with, while he was taking a stroll in the village. He marries her and on their wedding night, Nanda Dulal emerges and strikes a matchstick while lighting up Pratap's cigarette, teasing him about the development of their deal.

After Nanda Dulal's death from a heart attack, his sons lose all of the money because of their carelessness. Problems arise when his grandson sells Nanda Dulal's house to Nikunja Pal. Nanda Dulal had hidden a significant amount of wealth in the garden of that property while alive. Thereon, he decides to stay in the neem tree nearby guarding all the wealth. He tries to inform his grandson about the hidden wealth, but he gets scared of Nanda Dulal's bhoot. Nanda Dulal is a harmless ghost, but to the outsiders, he is still a ghost. This is why Pratap gets fearful when Nanda Dulal initially appears in front of him. Nanda Dulal prefers to impose his trust on a complete stranger Pratap, for he doesn't trust the villagers at all. Pratap visualizes Nanda Babu under moonlight, and even taunts him for his sudden disappearances. The bhoot of Nanda Dulal explains that sudden lights provide a shock to his existence that makes him unable to hold his form back soon enough. This also adheres to the popular belief that ghosts are afraid of lights. He requests Pratap to marry his ailing grandson's only daughter. When Pratap refuses, Nanda Dulal comes up with the proposal for his hidden wealth. Pratap irritably lights the torch to make Nanda Dulal disappear, but he returns. Nanda babu reasons that practice makes everything possible. Nanda babu has spent his entire life worrying about the wellbeing his family. He doesn't deter from this even after death, and reluctantly agrees for a five percent commission for Pratap. However, Pratap doesn't take the five gold coins even after the successful completion of the expedition, when he finds that he has fallen in love with Nanda Dulal's grandson's daughter. Nanda Dulal's tale is infused with comic elements to the brim.

His appearance, origin, banter with Pratap, the plan and its execution is dealt with humour. The horror element in this tale is the fact that there is none, even while it still deals with a ghost. The humorous tone in the story doesn't alter in the zone of adventure that these two embark on, for their specific interest. However, at the end the dual interests of Pratap and Nanda Dulal merge into one, and it ends on a happy note for the viewers.

In Bengal, horror and comedy coexist to form their own genre. The approach is balanced throughout. The treatment of horror and supernatural lends this distinct tone in *Jekhane Bhooter Bhoy*. This film is distinctive in the way that there is an eerie tone in the narrative, but there also a comic episode at the end. In the first tale, Anath babu becomes a ghost in the process of searching for it. In the second one, everyone had expected Simon to resemble a person, but he was none other than a black cat. In the third tale, the ghost was a person whose form hasn't shifted through time because of his concern for his family. The emphasis on the variedness of horror and the supernatural is noticeable in all of these three tales. Tarinikhhuro lends a composite impact of horror in the narrative effectively, for he holds the entire film together.

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